

On the Efficacy of Fingerprint-Based mmWave Beamforming in NLOS Environments: Experimental Validation

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Abstract—Fingerprint-based millimeter-wave (mmWave) beamforming is attracting growing attention due to its efficacy in reducing beam search/alignment time and subsequently decreasing channel estimation overhead to a negligible rate. This technique entails offline measurement collection to construct a dataset comprising potential high-gain beam directions, with location serving as a feature (fingerprint). The fingerprint-based mmWave beamforming is the inverse process of the localization. Assuming that the User Equipment (UE) possesses its position estimate, a machinery determines a set of candidate beams (beamforming codebook) based on the measurements within the dataset that are collected at proximate locations to the UE. The results in existing works, however, are often based on abstract models (often, the two-ray model), simulation results (typically based rays tracing simulator), and, in many cases, the outdoor environment with high probable Line-Of-Sight (LOS) link. In an effort to understand the extent and potential of such a technique, we have carried out a real-world experiment in an indoor office environment with high Non-LOS (NLOS) probability. We have trained a neural network model that provides the candidates' beams given a UE location. Although the results show an average beamforming gain of 17 dB, there is a considerable gap with respect to the highest possible beamforming gain obtained through exhaustive search.

Index Terms—mmWave, beamforming, fingerprint, machine learning, experimental validation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sub-6 GHz transmissions exhibit the features of rich-scattering channels, a phenomenon often modeled by Rayleigh fading. This model posits that the Angle-of-Arrivals (AoAs) of rays with high power vary independently in each channel coherence space. The latter is approximately equivalent to half the wavelength that is in the order of millimeters in the case of millimeter-wave (mmWave) communications. Consequently, the rich-scattering model, if it applies to the mmWave channel, suggests that neighboring User Equipments (UEs) separated by distances greater than the coherence distance experience uncorrelated AoAs. ¹ However, the sensitivity of mmWave transmissions to blockages results in a sparse channel structure, wherein only a limited number of scattered rays effectively reach the receiver. Building on this premise, it has

been presumed that AoAs of potential beams, pointing toward the direction of rays with strong power, remain correlated beyond the channel coherence distance [1]–[3]. This conjuncture has been validated to a certain extent in the presence of Line-Of-Sight (LOS) link, the two-ray model, and/or a static environment (absence of moving obstacles) [4]. This pivotal observation/assumption serves as the cornerstone of fingerprint beamforming technique [1], [2], [5], [6].

A. Related Work

The mmWave fingerprint technique has emerged as a promising method for accelerating beam search times by confining the search to a concise set of potential beams. For example, the IEEE 802.11ad standard relies on exhaustive search strategies for optimal transmit antenna beams, resulting in prolonged setup times [7]. In an effort to expedite the search time stipulated by the IEEE 802.11ad standard, the authors of [5] proposed a fingerprint technique involving the collection of offline dataset pertaining received signal strength (RSS) as a fingerprint of the WiFi signal along with the corresponding beams' directions. The results and conclusions are build upon a ray tracing simulator.

Other works on mmWave beamforming fingerprint adhere to the same principle but consider the location as the fingerprint feature rather than RSS [1], [2], [6]. The optimal beam is determined by matching the UE location to a pre-existing fingerprint dataset that contains a list of proximate locations and their corresponding optimal beams' directions. Restricting the search space to the beams associated with the UEs in the same vicinity significantly showed efficacy in reducing the search time. In [1], [2], the authors considered the scenario of vehicle-to-infrastructure mmWave communications and proposed a location aided beamforming approach. The main premise is that UEs' channels are highly correlated within a given vicinity. As per the proposed fingerprint-based beamforming method, a comprehensive fingerprint dataset is constructed based on data points from diverse locations within the designated area. Leveraging GPS-derived location information, the UE (vehicle) queries the fingerprint dataset, gaining insights into potential pointing directions of high-gain beams. Moreover, the authors in [1] advocated for the inclusion of environmental details in real time, such as nearby vehicles

¹Given to reciprocity of the channel, the same results apply for the Angle-of-Departures (AoDs). In the rest of the paper, we focus on the AoAs and the same results apply to the AoDs given the aforementioned uplink-downlink channel duality.

awareness, in conjunction with UE location information. The real time data supplementary information about the objects in the environment served to further refine the pool of potential beams, thereby reduce the search time.

B. Problem Statement

In existing literature, fingerprint techniques operate on the premise that high-gain beams' directions exhibit a high degree of correlation within a specified vicinity. Validation of these methodologies often relies on abstract models (e.g., the two-ray model), ray tracing simulators, and/or the assumption of a high likelihood of LOS links. However, recent experimentation conducted within an indoor office environment over the 28GHz band has cast doubt on this conventional understanding [8]. Findings from this study indicated that the two-ray model falls short in capturing the intricacies of the mmWave channel, prompting a five-ray model as a more accurate representation [8]. Furthermore, discrepancies were observed in comparison with the predictions of the ray tracing simulator. The adoption of the five-ray model introduces additional uncertainty regarding the correlation between high-gain beams' directions of UEs within a given vicinity, particularly in NLOS environments. These findings raise questions about the efficacy of fingerprint techniques, especially in environments with a high probability of NLOS links and in the presence of dynamic objects such as the case of indoor office environments.

The discrepancy in performance underscores the necessity for further research endeavors to elucidate the intricate dynamics of mmWave propagation in real-world indoor environments. The aim is to enhance the robustness and reliability of fingerprint-based beamforming techniques, particularly in scenarios fraught with NLOS propagation and dynamic environmental conditions.

C. Contributions

In an endeavor to elucidate the scope and efficacy of location-based fingerprint mmWave beamforming technique, we conducted a real-world experiment in a highly NLOS indoor office environment. The experimental setup involved placing a 28 GHz transmitter at one end of the corridor (hallway) and relocating a horn antenna receiver to various offices and different places within each office. Mounted on a rotating platform, the receiver precisely measured the power of received signals from all angles (360°) with one-degree accuracy. The experiment took place in a real-world setting during working hours, thereby introducing realistic environmental factors such as human presence and diverse obstacles, including experimental apparatus and furniture. Additional details on the used equipment and experiment parameters are provided in Section II-A.

In the offline dataset collection phase, each measurement point corresponds to the power profile of the received signals from all directions with one-degree accuracy, along with the precise receiver's 2D location. We utilize a machine learning approach that leverages the dataset, specifically the beams' parameters (width and direction) at locations within the vicinity

Fig. 1: Experiment environment.

of the UE. The output of trained machine learning model is a set of beams' directions and widths that serve as a codebook for beam search by the UE. In particular, we consider the Deep Neural Network (DNN) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture. To assess the effectiveness of location-based fingerprint beamforming mmWave technique, we allocate 30% of the collected data for testing purposes and 70% to train the neural network. The performance analysis of the fingerprint technique encompasses various parameters, including the size of the considered neighborhood and localization precision.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We provide the experiment setup and preliminary results in Sec. II. In Sec. III, we delve into the details of the developed location-based fingerprint technique. The results and conclusion are presented in Sections IV and V, respectively.

II. EXPERIMENT SETUP AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

A. Experiment setup

The measurements were carried out in a dynamic environment during working hours, encompassing a 110m long, 1.8m wide corridor bordered by offices and laboratories with diverse dimensions, all characterized by a high likelihood of NLOS conditions. Within this context, obstacles, including moving humans and furniture/equipment, displayed notable disparities in their occurrence, placement, and size from one laboratory or office to another. The transmitter was positioned at one end of the hallway, while the receiver was placed at various locations throughout the area. The measurements' locations included different offices, laboratories, as well as positions within the hallway itself. Measurements were also collected around the hallway intersection corners. Fig.1 illustrates the experiment environment, showcasing representative obstacles. The spacing between successive measurement points was approximately 1 foot (30 cm).

We used a narrowband sounder, transmitting a 28 GHz continuous-wave tone at 22 dBm into a 10 dBi horn with 55° half-power beamwidth in both elevation and azimuth. The receiver had a 10° (24 dBi) horn mounted on a rotating platform, allowing a full angular scan every 400 ms with 1° azimuthal angle sampling. The receiver recorded power samples at a rate of 740 samples/sec, with a 20 kHz receive

Fig. 2: Samples of azimuthal radiation patterns at a given location and their neighborhood locations.

bandwidth and effective noise figure of 5 dB. The system was calibrated to assure absolute power accuracy of 0.15 dBm. The sounder’s high dynamic range allowed reliable path loss measurements up to 171 dB with directional antenna gains. Although the proposed framework is not specific to a given propagation environment, the experimental results provided in this work pertain to the indoor office environment.

We collected measurements from around 700 different locations. At each location (measurement point), we ran the system for 10 sec where the sounder rotated with a speed of 150 rounds per minute, i.e., 2.5 rounds per second. As the received power was collected for each 1° azimuthal angle, we obtained measurements with an approximate size of $2.5 \times 10 \times 360 \times 700 = 9000 \times 700$. The receiver kept record of both the received power and their associated azimuthal angles, with the reference direction being the geodetic north (true north).

B. Preliminary results

In an initial experiment, we examined the radiation patterns at various locations, within different offices, and their neighboring areas, each of 3-meter radius. Initially, we expected to find a highly similar radiation pattern at the nearest location of the receiver. However, it is noteworthy that we encountered instances where measurements from two nearby locations revealed entirely dissimilar AoA profiles, as depicted in Figs. 2a and 2c. Conversely, similarities were observed at close locations, but not the nearest, as illustrated in Figures 2a and 2b. This observation leads to the conclusion that although the UE may find similar AoAs power profile at the nearest location, it is not always guaranteed with high certainty. Furthermore, the performance of the technique depends on the size of the considered neighborhood zone.

III. MACHINE LEARNING AIDED FINGERPRINT MMWAVE BEAMFORMING

The key idea behind the proposed fingerprint mmWave beamforming technique is to leverage the potential similarities among high-gain beams’ directions (dominant rays’ AoAs) of UEs located in close proximity. Specifically, we utilize measurements collected offline (e.g., during the deployment

phase, well before data transmission) on AoAs to construct a codebook that aggregates the directions and widths of high-gain beams collected around a given location. During data communications (online), the UE sends its location to the Base Station (BS), which in return shares the set of potential beam directions and widths (codebook). Subsequently, the UE selects the beam that maximizes its beamforming gain. The phases involved—collecting measurement data, designing the codebook, and beam selection—are described in detail below.

A. Offline Measurements Collection

The collection of measurements, as well as the training of the machine learning model that generates the beamforming codebook based on the UE location, are conducted offline. These processes can occur during the deployment phase of the BS, prior to its activation for users’ service. It is typical for service providers to gather measurements during the deployment phase to fine-tune configuration parameters such as antenna tilt and transmit power.

Once the BS is operational, the UEs can continue supplying the BS with more measurements. This is possible when an UE is in idle period and there is no data exchange with the BS. For example, during low-traffic periods such as nighttime, the BS may collect measurements from idle UEs. This functionality is already incorporated in existing standards such as LTE and is known as the radio resource control (RRC) protocol/mode [9]. Such a feature can enhance codebook accuracy by facilitating more measurements. Additionally, it offers the advantage of updating the machine learning model in response to environmental changes (e.g., new constructions) in an automated fashion without the intervention of the service provider.

Measurements are systematically gathered offline from various locations within the coverage area of the BS. At each location with coordinates (x, y) , the procedure entails establishing a narrow beam and incrementally rotating it with a small step, similar to exhaustive search. A beam is considered to be γ -optimal if its achieved power falls within γ dB gap with respect to the maximum received power $P_{\text{Max}}(x, y)$. The maximum received power is determined through exhaustive search considering a narrow beam with a width of 5° and an

angle precision of 1° . For each location, the receiver capture the widest γ -optimal beam, defined by its direction $\theta(x, y)$ and width $w(x, y)$, alongside the coordinates of the measurement location (x, y) . Subsequently, this data is transmitted to the BS for further processing. The outcomes of this data refinement stage comprise a set of beams that are γ -optimal and their corresponding locations. The set of data is in the form

$$(\Theta, \mathbf{W}) = \{(\theta(x, y), w(x, y)) | (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}\},$$

where $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$ is the space of the measurement points' locations.

B. Offline Codebook Design: Deep Neural Network

The BS leverages the acquired dataset to train a Deep Neural Network (DNN), establishing a parametric mapping denoted as $g(\cdot, \cdot)$. This mapping takes as input the 2D location (x, y) of a UE, along with the parameters of the location-based N -nearest γ -optimal beams, defined by the sets $\Theta^N(x, y) = \{\theta_n | n \in 1..N\}$ and $\mathbf{W}^N(x, y) = \{w_n | n \in 1..N\}$. Subsequently, the output of the DNN is K pairs of direction and width.

$$(\hat{\mathbf{W}}(x, y), \hat{\Theta}(x, y)) = g(\mathbf{W}^N(x, y), \Theta^N(x, y)). \quad (1)$$

Here, $(\hat{\mathbf{W}}(x, y), \hat{\Theta}(x, y)) = \{\hat{w}_k, \hat{\theta}_k | k \in 1..K\}$ refers to the codebook parameters at the location (x, y) and of size K .

We adopt the MLP as an architecture for the neural network, suggesting a fully connected neural network. We derive the optimal set of the parameters by training the neural network using 70% of the measurements. The loss function is defined as the discrepancy between the maximum received power $P_{\text{Max}}(x, y)$, obtained through exhaustive search, and the power $\hat{P}_{\hat{\mathbf{W}}, \hat{\Theta}}(x, y)$ achieved through scanning the codebook defined through $(\hat{\mathbf{W}}(x, y), \hat{\Theta}(x, y))$. Specifically, we employ the Mean-Square-Error (MSE) to compute the loss function, denoted by \mathcal{L} :

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y) = ||P_{\text{Max}}(x, y) - \hat{P}_{\hat{\mathbf{W}}, \hat{\Theta}}(x, y)||^2 \quad (2)$$

where

$$\hat{P}_{\hat{\mathbf{W}}, \hat{\Theta}}(x, y) = \max_{k \in 1..K} \hat{P}_{\hat{w}_k, \hat{\theta}_k}(x, y). \quad (3)$$

Here, $\hat{P}_{\hat{w}_k, \hat{\theta}_k}(x, y)$ denotes the received power achieved by considering the beam width \hat{w}_k and direction $\hat{\theta}_k$.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the neural network comprises an input layer, D hidden layers, and an output layer, with D representing the network's depth. The j th hidden layer ($j = 1..D$) contains M_j neurons. These neurons perform mathematical operations on their inputs and subsequently apply an activation function, $a_{i,j}[\cdot]$ where $i \in 1..M_j$, to generate signals forwarded to the subsequent layer. The output layer consists of $2 \times K$ neurons, with each pair being responsible for estimating the direction and width $(\hat{\theta}_k, \hat{w}_k)$ of a potential beam in the codebook. The propagation rules within the hidden layers are expressed as follows. For $j \in 1..D$ and $i \in 1..M_j$, the output of the i th neuron in the j th hidden layer is given by:

Fig. 3: DNN architecture for fingerprint mmWave beamforming.

$$v_{i,j} = a_{i,j}[t(\mathbf{u}_{j-1}, \mathbf{c}_{i,j}, b_{i,j})]. \quad (4)$$

Here, $a_{i,j}[\cdot]$, \mathbf{u}_{j-1} , and $\mathbf{c}_{i,j}$ represent respectively the activation function, input, and the weights vector pertaining the transition from i th neuron to the j th hidden layer. The function $t(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ denotes a linear transformation, and $b_{i,j}$ refers to a scalar bias. In Fig. 3, $\mathbf{b}_j = (b_{1,j}, \dots, b_{M_j,j})$ denotes the bias vector for the j th layer. The output layer correspond to the $(D + 1)$ th layer, indexed by O :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\theta}_k &= a_{2k-1,O}[t(u_D, \mathbf{c}_{2k-1,O}, b_{2k-1,O})] \\ \hat{w}_k &= a_{2k,O}[t(u_D, \mathbf{c}_{2k,O}, b_{2k,O})] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The linear transformation $t(\cdot, \cdot)$ is defined as

$$\begin{cases} t(\mathbf{u}_{j-1}, \mathbf{c}_{i,j}, b_{i,j}) = \mathbf{c}_{i,j}^T \mathbf{u}_{j-1} + b_{i,j} \\ t(u_D, \mathbf{c}_{k,O}, b_{k,O}) = \mathbf{c}_{k,O}^T \mathbf{u}_D + b_{k,O} \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

for $i \in 1..M_j$ and $k \in 1..K$. We use the gradient descent technique to minimize the loss function \mathcal{L} by iteratively moving in the direction of steepest descent as defined by the negative of the gradient [10]. In particular we use the stochastic gradient descent (SGD) that updates the weight parameters after evaluating the loss function \mathcal{L} for each sample. That is, rather than summing up the loss function results for all the samples then taking the mean, SGD updates the weights after every training sample is analysed [10].

C. Online Beam-Steering

We assume that the BS has access to the UE location (x, y) [6]. Consequently, the BS considers, as input, the beam and direction vector $(\mathbf{W}^N(x, y), \Theta^N(x, y))$ pertaining to the N nearest data points location-wise to the UE from the

dataset collected offline. The DNN’s output is a beamforming codebook comprising the parameters (directions and widths) of K beams. This codebook is subsequently shared with the UE for beam search. Beam selection, also commonly termed beam training, involves consulting the codebook to select the beam configuration that maximizes the array gain. Essentially, beam selection entails systematically testing each element of the codebook and selecting the one that yields the maximum received power.

As per the considered beam selection technique, the UE steers the beam according to the directives provided by the codebook. However, this process relies on an implicit assumption regarding a reference direction (i.e., direction 0°) that must be known by both the BS and the UE, and must align with the reference direction considered during the measurement phase. To illustrate, consider a scenario where one codebook entry specifies the beam direction as 90° . In such a case, the UE must first determine the reference direction (0°) and then orient the beam 90° . Establishing a reference direction can be accomplished through various means [11]–[19], with one common approach being to utilize geodetic directions such as true north, which can be easily accessed via the digital compass integrated into the UEs [11].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To assess the performance of the fingerprint mmWave beamforming technique, we divide the dataset into training and testing sets, utilizing 70% of the measurements (comprising location coordinates and beams’ widths/directions) to train the neural network and reserving the remaining 30% for testing purposes. Notably, our dataset encompasses measurements collected from approximately 700 distinct locations, suggesting that 210 measurement points are allocated for testing. For the neural network training phase, we feed the neural network with beams parameters at N neighborhood measurement points obtained from the offline collected dataset. The neural network architecture includes an input layer, an output layer, and $D = 4$ hidden layers, each containing $M_j = 256$ neurons. As discussed previously, the input data size is fixed at $2 + 2N$, consisting of (x, y) coordinates and N directions and their corresponding widths. Similarly, the output size is set to K pairs of directions and widths, resulting in a total of $2K$ output parameters. In particular we fix K to be equal to 5.

We conduct an analysis of the fingerprint technique’s performance, focusing on the difference between the achieved power $\hat{P}_{\hat{W}, \hat{\Theta}}$ and the maximum one obtained through exhaustive search. The difference can be expressed as the square root of the loss function outlined in (2). To provide a comprehensive overview of the outcomes, we provide the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the max-to-achievable power gap, i.e., $P_{\text{Max}} - \hat{P}_{\hat{W}, \hat{\Theta}}$. The CDF allows us to determine the percentage of scenarios where the gap exceeds or falls below a predefined threshold.

In Fig. 4, we examine the scenario where the BS has access to the precise location of the UE. The figure illustrates the CDFs of the max-to-achievable power gap for various values

Fig. 4: The CDF of max-to-achievable gain for different values of N .

Fig. 5: The CDF of max-to-achievable gain in presence of localization error

of N . Notably, we observe that the fingerprint technique exhibits a significant gap between the achieved and optimal beamforming gains, with $P_{\text{Max}}(x, y) - \hat{P}_{\hat{W}, \hat{\Theta}}(x, y)$ exceeding 12 dB for over 50% of cases when $N = 5$. Furthermore, the gap exceeds 10 dB with high probability and consistently across all scenarios. It is important to highlight that the achievable fingerprint-based beamforming gain, with respect to the received power by an isotropic antenna, ranges from 13 dB to 28 dB with an average of 17 dB. Furthermore, the figure shows an increase in the gain as N increases. However,

this increase is marginal. As N increases, the phenomenon can be attributed to the inclusion of beams at more distant locations in the training process. These beams are more likely to have uncorrelated AoAs profile with the one of the UE, thus they are less informative about the optimal beam direction and width.

Although in the experiment we were able to obtain the receiver location with centimeter precision, real-time information on UE location transmitted to the BS can be subject to higher uncertainty in practical scenarios. To simulate this, we introduce artificial errors to the 2D coordinates (x, y) of the UE, assuming Gaussian distributions with zero mean and variances σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 , respectively. We consider the case where $\sigma_x^2 = \sigma_y^2 = \sigma^2$. The results, depicted in Fig. 5 for $N = 5$, highlight that beyond a reasonable localization precision, such as $\sigma = 1$ meter, the beamforming gain becomes sensitive to localization errors, resulting in significant degradation in achievable gain. Consequently, in practice, the performance of the fingerprint technique depends not only on the correlation of beams among UEs in the same vicinity but also on localization precision, making the technique susceptible to performance instability.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have carried out a real-world experiment to investigate the efficacy of fingerprint mmWave beamforming in NLOS environment. In particular, the indoor office environment is considered. The main motivation behind this study is the concern raised by recent studies about the adopted two-ray model and ray tracing simulators that may not accurately capture the real behavior of the mmWave channel, especially in NLOS environments [8]. While the results show an average beamforming gain of 17 dB with the adoption of the fingerprint technique, there is still a gap compared to the maximum achieved power obtained through exhaustive search. We believe there is room for enhancement to approach the maximum gain while maintaining a short beam selection time.

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